

Big data classification based on improved parallel k-nearest neighbor

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ABSTRACT

In response to the rapid growth of many sorts of information, highway data has continued to evolve in the direction of big data in terms of scale, type, and structure, exhibiting characteristics of multi-source heterogeneous data. The k-nearest neighbor (KNN) join has received a lot of interest in recent years due to its wide range of applications. Processing KNN joins is time-consuming and inefficient due to the quadratic structure of the join method. As the number of applications dealing with vast amounts of data develops, KNN joins get more sophisticated. The authors seek to save money on computer resources by leveraging a large number of threads and multiprocessors. Six popular datasets are used to apply the method and evaluate the sequential and parallel performance of the KNN technique. These datasets are used to compare the sequential and parallel performance of the KNN method. When compared to a matching multi-core solution, the final implementation saves computing resources. It has been optimized to utilize as little RAM as possible, allowing it to manage high-resolution photo data without sacrificing efficiency. The authors will use the technique they presented using Spark Radoop. Our performance research validates the supplied method's efficacy and scalability.

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1. INTRODUCTION

At times, large amounts of data might be difficult to comprehend and even analyze [1], [2]. This challenge can be solved by using data mining techniques, which may be used to derive information from the data collected. The twenty-first century is the era [2] in which there is an enormous quantity of data, and that number is growing at an alarming rate. When dealing with such large amounts of data, the usual performance of computers is insufficient, and more intelligence is required to keep up with the current expansion of big data [3]–[17]. High-performance computing (HPC) should be taken into account while designing and creating software since it has the potential to increase computation speed while also giving more accurate results at a lower total cost than traditional computing [18]–[25]. HPC may be classified into a variety of categories, the most prominent of which are: computer clusters, grid computing, cloud computing, graphical processing units (GPU), microprocessors, and field programmable gate array (FPGA) [4], [20]–[22], [24].

In order to get high performance at the GPU level, it is possible to employ distributed memory programming with several processors, which is one of the ways that was used to achieve this outcome.

High-speed computing may be used to deal with large amounts of data in a variety of ways, one of which is through parallelizing machine learning algorithms and other methods. As a result of the simplicity and effectiveness with which it classifies data, the k-nearest neighbors (KNN) algorithm [26]–[41], is one of the most extensively used machine learning methods. KNN is a classification strategy that selects the item to category based on its proximity to the nearest point in the training set. If this approach is compared to other algorithms, it is considered to be straightforward, capable of dealing with a noisy dataset, and capable of producing decent results. The algorithm's disadvantage, on the other hand, is that it is difficult to compute and that the cost of putting it into practice is significant, as previously said. The method's parallel construction is utilized to reduce the complexity of the computation as well as the time required to do the distance calculation for each point in the dataset. As a result, the purpose of this article is to accelerate the KNN method through the use of multiple threads and multiple processors, thereby reducing the time required to run the algorithm.

Outlier identification, classification, molecular motion analysis, geographic databases, and pattern recognition are just some of the applications for which the KNN join and its variations have lately received a great deal of interest. It has also been stated that the performance of the popular k-means or k-medoid classification algorithms may be greatly enhanced by incorporating KNN joins into the process. When two relations, R and S, are joined together, the KNN join is performed. It yields every point in one relation R and the top-k nearest points in the other relation S. When dealing with a high-dimensional dataset, we take into consideration the difficulty posed by determining the k nearest neighbors of a query point. In order to efficiently handle this problem, we want to improve the performance of an existing method by parallelizing it as well as making it more tolerant to stragglers. While the KNN issue is not a new concept, it is frequently employed as a first step in a wide range of real-world applications, including genomics and customized search, network security, and web-based recommendation systems. As data and dimensionalities expand in the age of big data, KNN algorithms are frequently found to be a bottleneck. There is a large amount of research on the topic of quick closest neighbor retrieval [32]–[41].

An implementation of the parallel KNN technique based on MapReduce with a heterogeneous cluster was published in a work by [42] and it was carried out by employing the block nested loop strategy for KNN-joins. Data is partitioned into equal-sized blocks during the map stage, and these blocks are then subdivided into buckets during the sort step. Following that, during the reduce phase, the reducer does a block nested loop KNN join for each bucket that will be saved as depth first search (DFS) files, and the procedure is repeated for each bucket that will be stored as DFS files. Analysis of the findings revealed that the partitions were balanced with respect to the running duration and that speedup increased with the increasing size of the cluster. Communication using Hadoop block R-tree join, on the other hand, was found to be twice as effective as communication using Hadoop Z-value KNN Join. Furthermore, researchers discovered that as the dimension of communication increases, there is a decrease in recall and precision, leading to a lower ability to reach more than the average. It was published in the Journal of Scientific Computing in 2012 that a second study by Sismanis *et al.* [43] used the KNN algorithm for greater dimension with multi-core processors in the graphics processing unit (GPU). The parallelization of the KNN algorithm in the sorting process is accomplished through the use of truncated bitonic sorting techniques (TBiS). According to the conclusions of the study, it was found that the performance of the GPU with TBiS outperforms that of the sort and pick procedures.

Rajani *et al.* [44] investigated parallel k-nearest neighbor execution using tree-based data structures in open multi-processing) and the Galois framework. To implement KNN in OpenMP, four different forms of threading can be employed: 1, 4, 8, and 16 threads. Amdahl's law was used to assess how much quicker the implementation was compared to the original. With modified national institute of standards and technology (MNIST) datasets, the researchers observed that ball trees beat k-d trees in terms of performance in higher dimensions. They also discovered that ball trees are more efficient than Scikit-learn in Python when compared to other machine learning techniques. However, when the size of the datasets shrinks, the processing time gets faster, with a linear speedup for the datasets as the size of the datasets decreases. In [45]–[48] produced an OpenCL-based implementation of the KNN method for usage on FPGA and GPU systems, which was published in the Journal Scientific Reports. In order to allow the researchers to do distance calculation and distance ranking in parallel, they performed the bubble sort after data was sent from the CPU to the FPGA. Initially, a parallel distance calculation is carried out to estimate the distance between each item, and then a sorting operation is carried out to discover which of the items has the k-smallest distance between them. According to the findings of the study, when it comes to calculating speed, the GPU surpasses the CPU. When the average is used, the FPGA version of Joule, on the other hand, surpasses the GPU implementation. KNN performance depends on k and the proximity measure. If k is too low, the test sample will be impacted by noisy points and may overfit. Alternatively, if k is too high, the neighborhood may not adequately represent the class. In this study, we evaluated k values of 1, 10, and 100 (fine, medium, and coarse neighborhoods) to see if the model's accuracy was influenced.

Also, we used several distance metrics to evaluate their overall efficacy. When employing proximity-based classifiers, the size and range of the data values must be addressed. So, we used Z-score normalization to reduce problems with closeness predictions.

The purpose of this paper is to outline all of the particulars and requirements that must be met in order to construct to save money on computer resources by leveraging a large number of threads and multiprocessors. Six popular datasets are used to apply the method and evaluate the sequential and parallel performance of the KNN technique. These datasets are used to compare the sequential and parallel performance of the KNN method. This paper is outlined as: section 2 reviewed the related works regarding the recommended method, while sections 3 provided a brief discussion of the suggested methodology. Section 4 analyzed the evaluation results from the several experiments conducted in this study, while section 5 concluded the paper.

2. RELATED WORKS

2.1. Apache Spark Radoop

RapidMiner Radoop expands the typical RapidMiner in-memory capabilities by offering advanced operators that are built for execution in the Hadoop data processing system [47], [49]–[53]. Data transformations and sophisticated and predictive modeling are supported by more than 60 operators that operate on a distributed Hadoop cluster in the same way as Hadoop itself. RapidMiner Radoop makes use of RapidMiner Studio’s visual workflow designer to make the creation, execution, and maintenance of predictive analytics in Hadoop simpler. RapidMiner Radoop is available now. The code-free environment and built-in intelligence reduce the complexity of Hadoop, allowing you to concentrate on solving business challenges rather than being distracted by dead ends and technical obstacles. Radoop takes care of the workflow execution so that the user doesn’t have to worry about it. All of the calculations are done in the Hadoop cluster, which is where the data lives. This makes predictive analytics effective and highly scalable, even for terabytes and petabytes of data [6], [54]–[75].

RapidMiner is an addon that we developed to guarantee that Hadoop is fully integrated with RapidMiner [76]. Radoop, as a data science software platform, reduces the difficulties associated with data preparation and machine learning on Hadoop and Radoop Spark, as shown in Figure 1. Radoop provides additional operators for RapidMiner and communicates with the Hadoop cluster in order to complete task execution. All operations and data processing in RapidMiner Studio operate in parallel as a result of the use of SparkRM, which is part of the Hadoop ecosystem. This is achieved by the use of Apache Spark as the job execution tool, which allows for the expansion of use cases and the development of more powerful algorithms as compared to MLlib. Several Hive and Mahout data analytics routines were reused in this study due to the highly optimized nature of certain of their data analytics capabilities. This research developed an addition that would aid in the achievement of tight integration while also providing the same Hadoop features that are typically used in memory-based RapidMiner operations. First, the RadoopNest meta-operator is added to the RadoopNest meta-operator, which holds the general cluster settings such as the IP address of the Hadoop master node, and then the RadoopNest meta-operator is removed from the cluster. The remaining Radoop operators can only be used within this metaoperator and not outside of it [47], [51]–[53], [77].

Figure 1. Spark Radoop architecture

2.2. MapReduce

MapReduce is a programming methodology created by Google to handle large-scale data analysis. It is based on the Hadoop framework [11], [58], [78]–[81], [64]–[67], [69]–[71], [74]. It is employed in a wide variety of applications. Data mapping and reduction are accomplished through the use of the MapReduce framework [82]. Work is divided and distributed across the nodes in the distributed cluster using the map functions, which split and distribute the work among them. It is necessary for them to process a collection of key/value pairs in order to generate a set of intermediate key/value pairs. In order to resolve the results, the reduction functions aggregate all of the intermediate values that share a common intermediate key, as well as all of the work that must be done in order to resolve the results. Apache Hadoop is a Java-based framework for MapReduce implementation that is available as a free download [83]. It provides support for the processing of large datasets in a distributed computing environment, as well as the storage of data in a distributed file system that is both fault-tolerant and scalable (HDFS). Hadoop breaks the project down into smaller tasks, such as mapping and reducing tasks, and then combines them all together to complete the job. It is necessary to divide the input data into segments of a predetermined size, which are referred to as input splits [84]. Each map task is executed in a separate thread and deals with a logical partition of the data that is stored on the HDFS [6], [59], [60], [64], [65], [69], [72], [85].

3. METHOD

The KNN [1], [2], [44], [50], [54]–[56], [86]–[88], [4], [26], [27], [32], [37]–[42] is a non-parametric pattern recognition approach that is used for classification and regression in pattern recognition. In our example, the algorithm is utilized for classification, with the outcome being a class membership [89]. Objects are categorized by a majority vote of their neighbors, with the item being given to the class that has the greatest number of members among its k most immediate neighbors (k is a positive integer, typically small). If $k = 1$, then the object is simply assigned to the class of the object's nearest neighbor, which is the single nearest neighbor. Due to the fact that it memorizes the whole dataset, the KNN approach is considered a lazy learning classifier. Instead, it creates a discriminative model, similar to many of the classifiers that have been studied in the past (i.e., neural networks and decision trees). KNN plots nonlinear decision boundaries (Xie) on a graph and assists in assigning data points to one of the areas plotted on the graph [90]. It is the fundamental concept of KNN that if a test sample, which is an n -dimensional vector, is similar to a training sample, then it belongs to the training sample class [91]. In this case, the distance between the test sample and all of the other samples in the training set is calculated, and the sample is put into a class of the k -nearest samples, where k is an integer that shows how big the area around the test sample is.

The performance of KNN is influenced by the value of k and the proximity measure that is used. If the k value is set too low, the test sample will be influenced by the noisy points, and the test sample may suffer from an overfitting problem as a result. On the other hand, if the k number is excessively large, it is possible that the neighborhood may not accurately represent the true class. In this study, we examined k values of 1, 10, and 100 (i.e., fine, medium, and coarse neighborhoods) to investigate if the accuracy of the model was affected by the values of k . In addition, we employed a variety of different distance measurements to evaluate their overall effectiveness. One of the most essential difficulties to consider when using proximity-based classifiers is that they are sensitive to the dimensionality and range of the data values being considered. Therefore, we employed z -score normalization to reduce difficulties with proximity estimations, which we found to be particularly problematic. Figure 2 shows the KNN algorithm classifying a new sample.

Figure 2. The KNN algorithm classifying a new sample

When predicting the classification of a new sample point, KNN uses a database in which the data points have been divided into multiple classes to make its predictions. There is no stated requirement for a training step in the algorithm. It is based on the resemblance of features. KNN selects the k points in the labeled data-set that most closely reflect the characteristics of each new sample point and determines the class for that data point based on which label appears more frequently in the k picked points from the training data for each new sample point. Using the KNN algorithm, the k nearest neighbors is determined by computing the distance between the test and training data points. In a similar way to Kmeans, the distance computations account for the majority of the calculations. Even though KNN doesn't need as many iterations as K-means, it doesn't need as many iterations to get to a result either. Once the k nearest neighbors is found, a conclusion can be made.

In this section, various aspects of the implementation of the algorithm with the Radoop framework are discussed in further detail. There are various phases involved in the parallelization process. When it came to executing the experiments, we employed three supercomputers: one for testing and tweaking the circumstances under which they were ultimately carried out, and one to run them on a virtual machine cluster. Because we are working with enormous amounts of data, it is possible that a dataset has a significant number of transactions. The suggested approach is implemented as a series of "map and reduce" operations. The algorithm demonstrates the parallel implementation of K-means in MapReduce for $K = 1$ and two features, although the WordCount technique is used as an example in the majority of MapReduce examples. $(Cx1, Cy1)$ and $(Cx2, Cy2)$ are the feature values for the centroids of the two clusters, respectively. $(Cx1, Cy1)$ and $(Cx2, Cy2)$ are the feature values for the centroids of the two clusters. During the map phase, the outputs for each data point (x, y) are represented as a key-value pair, with keys being either 1 or 2 and referring to the cluster to which the data point is most closely associated. The key and values are computed using (1).

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Key} &= \text{Argmin} (1 \leq i \leq) (|x - Cxi| + |y - cyi|)^2 \\ \text{Value} &= (x, y) \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

A further step involves shuffling and sorting the key-value pairs. The pairings with the same key are routed to reduction functions, where the total of values for both features (x and y) is determined for all of the data in each cluster using the reduced functions (key). Then, the output is divided by the number of data points in the sample to get the new centroid values.

Proposed Parallel K-Nearest Neighbor

Input: S (Dense array) Output: T (Reduced array)

```

1  Begin
2      Run spark context (Slave)
3      Master connection is being listened to
4      Receive a dense array of data
5      Check the length of the columns M
6      Parallelize the data for processing;
7          N rows of data were gathered
8          do in parallel
9  Set the initial synaptic weights  $w_{ij}$  and thresholds  $\theta_j$  to tiny random values, such as [0, 1], and
   then repeat the procedure. Affect the learning rate parameter and the forgetting factor with
   modest positive values as well.
   for each  $r$  in  $R_i$  do
       Intilize KNN ( $r$ )with KNN ( $r$  .Si .K);
        $\sigma_k(r.S) = \max_{\sigma \in KNN(r .Si .K)} \text{distr}(r.B)$ ;

10 Calculate the output of the neuron at iteration T.
11 Make changes to the weights in the network.:  $w_{ij}(p + 1) = w_{ij}(p) + \Delta w_{ij}(p)$ , //  $i, j = 1, 2, \dots, n$ 
12 T should be sent as a reduction array.
13 Maintain a close connection
14 End

```

We focused on supervised classification algorithms created by Google, such as Naive Bayes, neural networks, k -nearest neighbors, and random forest. A summary of our experiments is shown in Table 1. The running times of the parallel generalized Hebbian algorithm (GHA) and parallel principal component analysis (PCA) on the identical hardware arrangement are presented in Table 2. Six unique, huge datasets were utilized to evaluate and compare the performance of the Apache Spark MLlib 2.0 package. Six datasets are available from the University of California, Irvine machine learning repository. The experimental architecture discussed in this article, in particular, consisted of a single Spark cluster that was developed in Java and used Apache Zeppelin 0.7.1 as an editor as well as an HDFS storage system. The Spark cluster is made up of several components, the most important of which are the master node, which is in charge of executing the driver application, and three worker nodes, which are in charge of data processing (including one worker node that runs on the master node). They all use the same software package and have the same

hardware setup (Intel® Core™ i7-6700 CPU running at 3.40 GHz, 16 GB of RAM, 8 logical cores, and Windows 10 operating system) (see Table 2).

The three worker nodes were each allotted a total of 48 GB of RAM. In each worker node, four executors were installed, each of which had four gigabytes of RAM and two processor cores. A total of three executors were installed on each worker on the master node, each of which had five gigabytes of RAM and two CPUs. A total of 16 GB of accessible RAM was made available to the driver process. As previously indicated, the MLlib was executed using the Scala 2.11.8 programming language in a Spark 2.2.1 cluster with Hadoop 2.7.3 providing distributed storage, with the results being stored in Hadoop 2.7.3. By changing the amount of RAM available to the executors in each worker node while keeping as many data partitions as the architecture could handle, the execution time was made as short as possible. Several big classification datasets were used in this work, which were collected from the University of California, Irvine data repository. Table 1 presents the important properties of these datasets, including the number of records, attributes, and classes for each dataset, within each dataset.

Table 1. Datasets description

Data	No of record	No of attributes	No of classes
Covtype	581012	54	7
Covtype-2	581012	54	2
Higgs	11,000,000	28	2
Botnet Attacks	7,062,606	115	10
Dota2	102944	116	2
SUSY	5,000,000	18	2

Table 2. System description

Parameter	Description
Operating system	Windows10
CPU	Intel® Core™ i7-6700 CPU @ 3.40 GHz with 8 logical cores
Memory	16 GB
Number of workers	3
Computational framework	Apache Spark 2.2.1
compatible framework	Radoop
Distributed storage system	HDFS (Hadoop 2.7.3)
Editor for code development	Apache Zeppelin 0.7.1
Language used for coding	Scala 2.11.8

Table 3. Confusion matrices description

Matrices	Predicted positive	Predicted negative
Actual positive	True positive (TP)	False negative (FN)
Actual negative	False positive (FP)	True negative (TN)

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In this section, the results of the experiments that were conducted and the discoveries that were obtained after applying the indoor positioning k-nearest neighbor algorithm that was described in the methodology are broken down and discussed. The effectiveness of parallel KNN is evaluated for accuracy and speed in terms of data and model parallel KNN, as well as for the efficacy of parallel KNN for accuracy and speed in terms of parallel KNN. In Table 3, we can find a description of the confusion matrix.

4.1. Accuracy

According to the data presented in the table that came before it, the formula for determining how accurate a test is is $(TP + TN)/(TP + FP + FN + TN)$. This represents the total number of true positive and true negative instances as a percentage of the total number of cases. Figure 3 demonstrates how significantly more effective the enhanced parallel KNN algorithm is in comparison to its predecessor.

4.2. Recall

The recall (also known as sensitivity) of a genuine positive is the ratio of the number of true positives to the total number of true positives. In mathematical terms, the recall formula is: $TP/(TP + FN)$. Using this method, we can determine how well our model performs in terms of identifying the real, genuine outcome. Figure 4 shows the recall of the improved parallel KNN algorithm compared with the original algorithm.

Figure 3. The accuracy of improved parallel KNN algorithm compared with original algorithm

Figure 4. The recall of improved parallel KNN algorithm compared with original algorithm

For we utilize KNN to build the model, we can get the highest level of accuracy possible when forecasting absences. KNN has the highest success rate when aiming to ensure that the availability forecast is as accurate as possible. In this case, KNN may use similarity-based learning approaches to locate the not-so-easy-to-access dataset, or agent predictability. Once the system has found trends in the similarities of an employee's absences, it may predict when the individual will call in absent the following time. This forecast has significant restrictions, but it is generally accurate. When an employee calls in sick, the KNN uses the information to construct future instances of the employee. In this strategy, the call center will have enough data to construct a data set that will be utilized to estimate the predictability of each employee's agent predictability set. We compare it to the most fundamental generic techniques. For each approach, based on these comparisons, we can see the strength of our technique, which is more accurate than all of the classic approaches available and competitive with other powerful state-of-the-art methodologies. We approach our strategy in the same way we did previously.

4.3. Execution time

The default calculation method is serial calculation. Serial computation is characterized by the fact that each calculation pass is scheduled to be performed on a single processor. If the calculations are triggered by a calculation script, they are run sequentially in the order in which they occur in the calculation script, unless otherwise specified in (2). Parallel computing divides each calculation pass into a number of smaller sub-tasks. All of the sub-tasks that are capable of running independently of one another are scheduled to be executed simultaneously on up to 64 or 128 threads, depending on the configuration. Figure 5 shows the execution time comparison of serial KNN vs IPKNN.

$$S_{\text{Latency}} = \frac{L_{\text{Serial}}}{L_{\text{Parallel}}} \quad (2)$$

Across all data and model sets, the IPKNN implementation outperformed the single-node KNN implementation in all of our studies. Figure 5 shows that data parallel KNN is significantly faster than single-node KNN. The number of cores influences how fast the computer performs. This experiment was carried out on Internet cluster 1. The main purpose was to better understand the algorithm by determining how it behaves as the number of processing cores on the machines increased. There are a few aspects that must be considered

when assessing the data. As a result, the dataset is divided into exactly the same number of pieces as the total number of cores in the cluster, resulting in an overall result of n pieces. As a result of this configuration, we can ensure that every available core is always working on one or more bits of data from the dataset. This enables us to fully utilize the Spark configuration, keeping in mind that it is recommended that the dataset be broken into chunks at least equal in size to those accessible on the cluster's number of cores. The slave node could only have one executor for the two-core experiment, and each executor could only use 15 GB of RAM.

Figure 5. Execution time comparison of Serial KNN vs IPKNN

5. CONCLUSION

As a result, the necessity to develop new methods for processing huge datasets in order to reduce time costs prompted the creation of a data categorization strategy based on parallel partitions. Despite the increased number of clusters, separating data into batches aids in decreasing the classification algorithm's reaction time and associated processing costs. Parallel implementation of the proposed technique on a large number of nodes was found to be approximately twice as fast. This study compared the performance of the suggested technique on six datasets, and the results are reported in this report. This technique, which may be applied to big data analysis in medical, industrial, and business sectors, among others, can accomplish massive data categorization in a short period of time. Some of Python's parallel programming constraints are novel, as are some of the limits of other programming languages. In comparison to other programming languages, Python has fewer references to learn and fewer applications to implement. Experiments for the technique were also conducted on a single computer, which resulted in a number of system failures and difficulties with limiting the time of the recommended algorithm, among other issues. Future study could look into running the parallel algorithm in the cloud, as well as running the KNN in parallel on larger datasets. These are merely a few ideas for future research. In the future, the problem will be overcome by altering the number of centroids in each batch as the batch size changes. Furthermore, determining how to identify appropriate starting centroids, which is still a significant challenge in classification, will aid in increasing the accuracy of the parallel batch classification method, which is now not very accurate.

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